

DISTRICT-WISE ANALYSIS OF GROWTH RATE AND VARIABILITY IN WHEAT AREA, PRODUCTION, AND PRODUCTIVITY IN VIDARBHA

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Abstract

The present study was conducted in eleven districts of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra with objective to study growth rate and variability in area, production, Productivity of wheat. This research paper was based on the secondary data and time series data of 20 years, the research divided the analysis into two periods: Period I (2003-04 to 2012-13) and Period II (2013-14 to 2022-23), along with an overall analysis for 2003-04 to 2022-23. The findings reveal a significant increase at the 1% level across all metrics for the entire period, with a 3.49% increase in cultivation area, a 5.67% rise in production, and a 3.10% growth in productivity in the Vidarbha region. Period I exhibited robust growth across these metrics, while Period II experienced a slowdown, particularly in cultivation area. Significant district-level variations in production and area indicate high variability, whereas productivity remained stable in districts such as Bhandara, Amravathi, and Wardha during the study period.

Keywords: Compound growth rate, Instability, Wheat, Vidarbha

Introduction

Agricultural growth is crucial for economic development. Researchers emphasize the need for sustainable agricultural growth, even if other sectors grow quickly. Economists agree that agriculture is essential for overall economic growth. To ensure steady economic progress, it is important to measure how different factors contribute to agricultural output. Key factors include area, yield, and production. Knowing the growth rates of these factors for any crop helps identify and address obstacles to faster agricultural development. Understanding these growth rates can guide policy decisions and resource allocation, ultimately enhancing productivity and economic stability. Furthermore, assessing the variability in these factors provides insights into regional disparities and potential areas for intervention. With this in mind, objective of this study is to study the performance of wheat in vidarbha region. The findings aim to inform strategies for improving agricultural practices and achieving sustainable growth in the region.

Material And Methods**Selection of study area:**

Wheat is crucial in Vidarbha as a staple food crop and a significant source of income for farmers. It thrives as a rabi crop in the region's agro-climatic conditions, fitting well into crop rotation practices. Wheat cultivation supports food security and benefits from government incentives, making it an integral part of Vidarbha's agricultural economy.

Study period:

The data for area, production, productivity of wheat district wise in Vidarbha region were collected for a period of 20 year from 2003-04 to 2022-23. The whole study period was divided into sub periods for area, production and yield: Period-I: 2003-04 to 2012-13, Period- II: 2013-14 to 2022-23 and Overall period: 2003-04 to 2022-23.

Analytical tools and techniques:**Estimation of Growth Rate**

The compound growth rates of area, production, productivity and price of wheat was estimated by using following exponential.

$$Y = ab^t$$

Where,

$$Y = \text{Area} / \text{Production} / \text{Productivity} / \text{Price}$$

t = Time Variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

Then the per cent compound growth rates 'r' was computed by using the following formula.

$$\text{CGR (r)} = [\text{Antilog} (\log b) - 1] \times 100$$

Where,

r = Compound growth rate

t- Test was used to check the significance of CGR

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{\text{S.E (d)}}$$

Where,

\bar{d} = Standard deviation

S. E (d) = Standard error

Measurement of Instability

The coefficient of variation was used to measure the variability in the area, production productivity of Wheat.

Coefficient of variation (CV):

$$\text{CV} = \text{SD} \div \text{AM} \times 100$$

Where,

CV is Coefficient of variation

SD is Standard deviation

AM is Arithmetic mean

Where, CV=Coefficient of variation (in %)

Results And Discussion**Compound growth rate of area, production and productivity of wheat:**

The estimation of growth rates of wheat crops was essential to analyze the expansion and effectiveness of wheat crop in the geographical boundary of any state or union territory. This type of studies helps us to understand the allocation of available resources in that state or union territory. The growth rates of productivity, production, area were computed to analyze their performance.

Growth analysis of wheat area, production and productivity has been calculated and depicted in table 1. reveals that during Period I, several districts in the Vidarbha region experienced positive growth in area, production, and productivity. However, Chandrapur and Gadchiroli districts did not follow this trend for the area, and Gondia district exhibited significant decline in area and production declining insignificantly. Notably, Amravati district recorded the highest growth rate for area at 17.01%, while Gondia district had the lowest at -5.67%, with Gondia district area being statistically significant at the 5% level and Amravathi being significant at 1%. Conversely, Amravati also registered the highest growth rate in production at 23.71%, significant at the 1% level. The compound growth rates for the area were generally positive across the Vidarbha region during Period I, indicating overall growth. The overall area under cultivation in the Vidarbha region grew significantly at a CAGR of 7.70%. Production growth was also significant at 13.85%, indicating effective use of the expanded area. Productivity growth was significant at 8.02%, reflecting substantial improvements in yield per unit area.

During Period II (2013-14 to 2022-23), many districts in the Vidarbha region experienced slower growth rates in the area under cultivation and production compared to Period I. In Period II, a trend of negative growth was observed in six districts for the area. With the exception of the area, production and productivity in Gadchiroli district showed negative growth. Akola had the highest growth rate for area at 7.81%, positively significant at the 1% level. Meanwhile, the most significant declines in growth rates for area and production were seen in Gadchiroli district at -6.03% and -7.43%, respectively, though these declines lacked statistical significance. The overall area under cultivation in the Vidarbha region grew slightly at 0.55%, a significant slowdown from the previous period. Production growth slowed to 7.09%, compared to

the robust growth in Period I. Productivity growth remained significant at 6.36%, reflecting continued advancements in yield per unit area. Over the entire 20-year period, the compound growth rates of area and production were positive in most districts, except for Gadchiroli (-3.61%) and Wardha (-2.54%), both significant at the 1% level. Gondia also showed a negative growth rate in terms of area (-1.16%), but this was not statistically significant. Nagpur district exhibited the highest growth rates for area, production, and productivity at 7.02%, 10.21%, and 2.98%, respectively, with the productivity growth rate being statistically significant at the 1% level. The overall area under

cultivation in the Vidarbha region grew moderately at a CAGR of 3.49%. Production growth was significant at 5.67%, reflecting effective use of the expanded area. Productivity grew significantly at 3.10%, indicating substantial improvements in yield per unit area.

The study by Patare *et al.* (2023) reported overall positive growth in area, production, and productivity during Period I and was showing contrasting findings with declining cultivation areas of wheat. Bhaviskar *et al.* (2020) reported contrasting findings, noting a decline in the growth rate of the wheat cultivation area in the Vidarbha region during the study period.

Table 1: District wise compound growth rate of Wheat in Vidarbha

Districts	Particulars	Period I (2003-04 To 2012-13)	Period II (2013-14 To 2022-23)	Overall Period CGR (%) (2003-04 to 2022-23)
Akola	Area	15.89	7.81**	3.40
	Production	22.29	10.53**	2.53
	Productivity	4.44	2.53	-0.70
Amravati	Area	17.01**	-4.14	5.20**
	Production	23.71**	-1.48	5.78**
	Productivity	5.71**	2.77	0.55
Bhandara	Area	3.20	-1.44**	0.58
	Production	7.06	0.20	3.03**
	Productivity	3.69*	1.67*	2.42**
Buldhana	Area	4.51	-1.62	2.75*
	Production	10.34	6.84	4.97*
	Productivity	5.59	8.60**	2.16
Chandrapur	Area	-1.85	-3.20**	-3.24**
	Production	5.99	1.01	-0.01
	Productivity	8.05**	4.37	3.35**
Gadchiroli	Area	-2.65	-6.03	-3.61**
	Production	4.15	-7.43	-1.69
	Productivity	6.59**	-0.73	2.04
Gondia	Area	-5.67*	3.60	-1.16
	Production	-3.71	9.42**	0.74
	Productivity	2.03	6.02	1.90*
Nagpur	Area	9.52**	3.20	7.02**
	Production	13.58**	12.34**	10.21**
	Productivity	3.72**	8.85**	2.98**
Wardha	Area	3.47	-1.42	-2.54**
	Production	6.42	3.57	-0.74
	Productivity	2.87*	5.09**	1.84**
Washim	Area	11.79	2.83	6.58**
	Production	17.29	9.68	8.44**
	Productivity	4.96	7.00	1.67
Yavatmal	Area	14.66*	5.94	5.82**
	Production	21.12*	10.98	6.16*
	Productivity	5.66*	4.77	0.32
Vidarbha	Area	7.70*	0.55	3.49**
	Production	13.85*	7.09*	5.67**
	Productivity	8.02*	6.36**	3.10**

** & * Significant at 1% & 5% level of significance respectively

Instability in Area, Production and Yield of Wheat

The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is a statistical measure of the relative variability expressed as a percentage. It provides insights into the stability or volatility of different aspects of agricultural performance, including area, production, and productivity. Higher CV values indicate

greater variability, while lower CV values suggest more stability. The variability in the cultivation area, production, and productivity of wheat was carefully assessed by calculating the coefficients of variation (C.V. %). Instability in Area, Production and Yield of Wheat using coefficient of variation has been calculated and depicted in table 2.

Table 2: Variability in area, production and productivity of wheat

Districts	Coefficient of Variation (%)		
	Area	Production	Productivity
Akola	46.84	71.17	24.85
Amravati	41.37	41.86	16.85
Bhandara	17.11	23.61	15.16
Buldhana	36.53	49.52	29.14
Chandrapur	24.70	27.76	27.53

Gadchiroli	35.70	37.48	25.98
Gondia	23.99	28.79	25.08
Nagpur	37.86	57.69	26.08
Wardha	26.92	31.72	19.03
Washim	45.67	67.50	32.38
Yavatmal	41.32	54.78	25.89
Vidarbha	24.91	38.50	25.99

From the above table it is inferred that High Variability in Production was observed in Akola (71.17%) Washim (67.50%) Yavatmal (54.78%) districts. High CVs indicate significant fluctuations in production over time. Moderate to High Variability was observed in Area of Akola (46.84%) Washim (45.67%) Yavatmal (41.32%) districts. Reflects considerable changes in the area under cultivation. Relatively Stable Productivity Bhandara (15.16%) Amravati (16.85%) Wardha (19.03%) lower CVs indicate more stable yield per unit area. Bhaviskar et al. (2020) reported consistent findings While there is high variability in area and production, indicating fluctuations, the consistent productivity in districts like Bhandara, Amravati, and Wardha. Bhopale, A.A., & Shende, N.V. (2021) reported are consistent. The high variability in production and area aligns with the high coefficient of variation seen in soybean input utilization and wheat production/area.

Conclusion and implications

From the study it may concluded that, Vidarbha region experienced a significant growth in wheat cultivation, with a 3.49% increase in area, a 5.67% increase in production, and a 3.10% increase in productivity, all significant at the 1% level. Period I experienced robust growth in area, production, and productivity, while Period II saw a slowdown, particularly in the area under cultivation. Overall, the region demonstrated positive growth, with notable district-level variations. High variability in production and area was observed in certain districts, indicating significant fluctuations over time. Productivity showed relative stability in districts like Bhandara, Amravathi, and Wardha. The high variability in production and area across districts highlights the need for targeted agricultural policies to stabilize these fluctuations.

Improving irrigation and adopting modern practices could enhance productivity consistency and support sustainable growth in Vidarbha.

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